

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.12 – Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s Platform

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	The D6.12 Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s Platform is the final report detailing the resources and actions undertaken to share UP2030’s key outputs and tools through the EU Mission’s Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Platform.			

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Contents

Executive summary.....	5
Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables.....	5
Acronyms.....	7
1 Introduction.....	8
1.1 Purpose and scope	8
1.2 Document structure	8
2 Methodology and approach	9
2.1 Overall approach	9
2.2 Roles and responsibilities	9
2.3 Coordination with relevant initiatives	10
3 Resources shared in the Mission’s Platform	11
3.1 Overview of the resources	11
3.1.1 Citizen Mapping Tool	11
3.1.2 Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality	12
3.1.3 TU Delft Planning Cycle	13
3.1.4 Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM).....	14
3.1.5 Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT).....	15
3.1.6 Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board	15
3.1.7 Presentation: How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?	16
3.1.8 Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)	17
3.1.9 UP2030 Service Platform	17
4 Dissemination and sharing activities.....	18
4.1 Upload of resources to the Mission’s Platform	18
4.2 Collaboration and liaison with the Mission’s Platform	18
4.3 Visibility and promotion	19
4.4 Outcomes	19
5 Conclusion	20

Figures

Figure 1: Citizen Mapping Tool as displayed on the Mission’s Platform.....	12
Figure 2: Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality as displayed on the Mission’s Platform.....	13
Figure 3: TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle as displayed on the Mission’s Platform	14
Figure 4: Spatial Justice Conceptual Model as displayed on the Mission’s Platform.....	14
Figure 5: Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool as displayed on the Mission’s Platform	15
Figure 6: Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board as displayed on the Mission’s Platform	16
Figure 7: Presentation “How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?” as displayed on the Mission’s Platform.....	16

Executive summary

This Deliverable (D) 6.12 – Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission's Platform, outlines the activities undertaken to share UP2030 results with the European Union (EU) Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Platform. The objective was to make the project's most transferable outputs accessible to Mission Cities and other stakeholders engaged in climate-neutral urban transitions.

The work was coordinated by Fraunhofer (project coordinator) and ICLEI Europe under Work Package (WP) 6, in close liaison with the NetZeroCities (NZC) Mission's Platform. The process included the identification, review, and upload of selected UP2030 outputs in line with the Mission's Platform's requirements.

A total of seven resources were shared:

- Citizen Mapping Tool
- Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality
- TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle
- Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM)
- Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT)
- Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board
- Presentation: How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?

At the time of submission of this deliverable, two additional resources were still under preparation to be shared on the Mission Platform:

- Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)
- UP2030 Service Platform

These materials cover themes such as participatory planning, stakeholder engagement, and spatial justice and were developed through WP2 and WP3 in collaboration with project partners and pilot cities. Each resource was reviewed for accuracy and relevance before publication.

Promotion of the shared resources has been carried out through UP2030's communication channels, including the project newsletter and social media, to ensure visibility among Mission Cities and stakeholders.

By sharing its outputs through the Mission's Platform, UP2030 contributes to the Mission's collective knowledge base and supports replication, capacity-building, and mutual learning among European cities working towards climate neutrality.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages' structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with ICLEI Europe, Fraunhofer, WP2, WP3, and WP6. The following table lists the deliverables that were input for this document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content presented here.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D2.4 — Interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality</p> <p>D3.2 — Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2</p> <p>D3.8 — Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 1</p> <p>D6.10 — Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1</p> <p>D6.11 — Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2</p>	<p>D6.11 — Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2</p>

The main target group for this deliverable is the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities community, particularly Mission Cities, sister projects (CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value), and other stakeholders involved in the Urban Planning and Design Cluster. The shared materials are intended for use by city administrations, practitioners, and researchers working on resilience, climate neutrality, and participatory urban planning.

This deliverable feeds into the final stage of the project (M36), when project outcomes are consolidated and made publicly accessible through the Mission’s Platform and UP2030’s communication channels. The content has been showcased on internal partner exchanges and references in project communication materials such as newsletters and the UP2030 channels. These actions aimed to promote visibility and encourage the continued use of UP2030 resources by Mission Cities and other interested stakeholders.

Acronyms

Please add all the acronyms mentioned in the document in alphabetical order.

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
M	Month
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NZC	NetZeroCities
SJBT	Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool
SJCM	Spatial Justice Conceptual Model
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of Deliverable (D) D6.12 is to describe the actions undertaken by UP2030 to share project results with the [Mission's Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Platform](#) (hereinafter referred to as Mission Platform) and related dissemination mechanisms. This document outlines how project outputs have been prepared and made available to contribute to the wider knowledge base of the EU (European Union) Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.

D6.12 defines the scope and approach applied to collect, curate, and communicate relevant materials developed within UP2030 in alignment with the Mission's Platform requirements. Additionally, it provides an overview of the processes used to facilitate the exchange of information across participating projects and stakeholders.

This report covers the period of UP2030 implementation Months 1-36 (M1-36) and focuses on the activities related to the dissemination of project results suitable for external sharing. It aims to ensure transparency and traceability of the project's contribution to the Mission's learning and knowledge-sharing framework.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: Presents the purpose, scope, and structure of the document.
- ❖ Section 2 – Methodology and approach: Describes the process adopted for identifying, curating, and preparing UP2030 resources for sharing with the Mission's Platform.
- ❖ Section 3 – Resources shared in the Mission's Platform: Summarises the key outputs selected for dissemination, outlining their thematic focus and relevance to the Mission's objectives.
- ❖ Section 4 – Dissemination and sharing activities: Details the mechanisms, channels, and collaborations used to share UP2030 results with the Mission's Platform and related initiatives.
- ❖ Section 5 – Conclusion: Provides a concise summary of the activities undertaken and reflects on the contribution of UP2030 to the broader Mission knowledge framework.

2 Methodology and approach

This section describes the methodological framework applied to prepare and share UP2030's key outputs with the Mission's Platform. The approach was designed to ensure that project outcomes were systematically identified and reviewed for dissemination in a way that aligns with the Mission's knowledge-sharing objectives and requirements.

The preparation of this deliverable was guided by the principle that the dissemination of project results should not only increase visibility but also support transferability and learning across European cities. Accordingly, the methodology aimed to establish a transparent, structured, and replicable process for selecting and sharing UP2030 results that are relevant to stakeholders.

The process built upon coordination structures already developed through clustering activities under "[D6.10 — Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1](#)" and "D6.11 — Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2", and leveraged the collaboration channels established with related Horizon Europe projects and Mission support initiatives such as the NetZeroCities (NZC).

2.1 Overall approach

The approach combined internal coordination within UP2030's consortium and external engagement with the Mission's Platform, as well as with related Horizon Europe projects. This ensured that the preparation and sharing of resources were consistent, complementary, and aligned with the broader Mission framework.

The process included the following steps:

- Identification of materials: Selection of project outputs suitable for sharing, based on their relevance, completeness, and potential for replication.
- Curation and standardisation: Review and adaptation of selected materials to align with the Mission's Platform requirements.
- Validation: Internal review by responsible partners to verify content accuracy and consistency.
- Coordination with Mission actors: Liaison with NZC, the Mission's Platform, and the Core Cluster to ensure alignment.
- Dissemination and documentation: Uploading and promotion of materials through the Mission's Platform and other relevant channels.

2.2 Roles and responsibilities

Coordination between UP2030 partners and NZC was maintained through periodic exchanges. The activities described in D6.12 were jointly coordinated by Fraunhofer and ICLEI Europe, under Work Package (WP) 6.

- Fraunhofer ensured overall oversight of the process, alignment with the Mission's communication framework, and verification of the resources selected for sharing. It maintained contact with representatives of the Mission's Platform and supported the review of materials before their submission.

- ICLEI Europe led the operational coordination of the sharing activities, liaising with NZC and Mission's Platform representatives to facilitate and accelerate the upload of UP2030 resources. In addition, it introduced and presented the shared resources during the Cluster meetings, informing sister projects about the uploads and fostering discussion on potential complementarities.

The actions were carried out collaboratively, with ICLEI Europe and Fraunhofer maintaining continuous communication to ensure that all materials shared through the Mission's Platform met the required accuracy and alignment with the objectives.

2.3 Coordination with relevant initiatives

The coordination activities related to D6.12 were built on the framework established through D6.10 and D6.11, which defined synergies between UP2030 and its sister projects [CLIMABOROUGH](#) and [Re-Value](#) (Core Cluster) as well as exchanges with NZC and the Mission's Platform (Exchange Cluster).

For the purpose of D6.12, coordination focused specifically on the operational aspects of sharing UP2030's results. Regular exchanges with NZC helped ensure that UP2030 resources met the Platform's requirements.

To foster complementarity and avoid duplication, and as part of the Urban Planning and Design Cluster, information on resources shared through the Platform was also communicated to cluster partners. This allowed CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value to be informed of the materials uploaded by UP2030 and to explore potential synergies or complementary dissemination actions.

Coordination was supported by the structures developed through previous clustering meetings, which provided an efficient channel for information exchange and alignment. This collaboration resulted in a consolidated list of UP2030 outputs selected for sharing and their subsequent upload to the Mission's Platform. The process ensured that all materials shared were accurate, complete, and consistent with the objectives.

3 Resources shared in the Mission's Platform

3.1 Overview of the resources

The materials shared by UP2030 through the Mission's Platform reflect the project's focus on supporting cities in accelerating their transition towards climate neutrality through participatory urban planning and design. The selected resources represent a combination of tools, conceptual frameworks, and methodological guidance developed under the WPs (notably WP2 and WP3) and validated through the project's pilot cities.

The resources were selected to provide Mission Cities and other urban practitioners with practical instruments to strengthen inclusive governance, participatory planning, and data-driven decision-making. These reflect UP2030's main practice-oriented and policy-relevant outputs and summarise the project's methodologies, tools, and insights that may support policy development and planning processes in Mission Cities.

The following paragraphs provide an overview of the resources shared, illustrating their thematic focus and contribution to the Mission's objectives.

3.1.1 Citizen Mapping Tool

The [Citizen Mapping Tool](#) is an open-source, map-based platform developed by the Technische Universiteit Delft Citizen Voice initiative that enables researchers and practitioners to design surveys containing geospatial questions. These questions allow respondents to provide information about locations they know or to identify points and areas directly on an interactive map. The tool supports multiple question types, including map-based pin placement, polygon drawing, and conventional multiple-choice responses.

This tool is designed to be intuitive and accessible to a broad range of users, including those with limited technical expertise. Its flexible and customisable structure allows cities, planners, and researchers to adapt survey content to their specific needs and urban contexts.

By enabling the collection of spatially explicit data from citizens and stakeholders, the Citizen Mapping Tool enhances participatory planning processes and provides planners with richer, place-based insights into community experiences, needs, and priorities. In doing so, it supports Mission Cities in strengthening participatory governance and integrating citizen perspectives into urban design and policy development.

Figure 1: Citizen Mapping Tool as displayed on the Mission’s Platform

3.1.2 Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality

The [Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality](#) was developed based on the participatory methodology applied within UP2030, designed to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to achieve their climate-neutrality targets. It provides a structured yet adaptable framework to guide municipal teams and practitioners through the main stages of stakeholder engagement, from initial planning and implementation to final evaluation.

The toolkit consists of a simple interactive checklist that allows users to expand each stage to access relevant tools, methods, and supporting resources. This design ensures ease of navigation and practical usability for city administrations, researchers, and local stakeholders involved in co-creation processes. Each step of the checklist is informed by the participatory urban-planning and design principles used in UP2030, helping cities identify needs, barriers, and drivers for change while co-creating shared visions for transformation.

Intended for flexible use across diverse contexts, the toolkit provides a consistent reference for structuring stakeholder engagement activities around urban climate transitions and supports the integration of participatory planning practices into Mission Cities’ ongoing climate-neutrality pathways.

Figure 2: Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality as displayed on the Mission’s Platform

3.1.3 TU Delft Planning Cycle

The [TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle](#) is a comprehensive strategic planning model designed to enhance urban sustainability and inclusivity by systematically incorporating participatory tools and methodologies into urban development processes. The model facilitates broad stakeholder engagement through a detailed, step-by-step planning cycle that helps cities structure their decision-making and ensure transparency throughout all stages of the transformation process.

The cycle provides a clear sequence of interconnected phases, guiding cities from the identification of local needs and challenges to the upscaling of tested solutions. Each phase promotes active involvement of citizens, planners, and decision-makers, encouraging co-design and shared ownership of strategies and interventions.

By embedding participation and reflection within each step of the planning process, the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle supports cities in aligning long-term sustainability objectives with locally relevant actions. It offers Mission Cities a practical reference for designing and implementing inclusive, data-informed, and iterative planning processes that can be adapted to different urban contexts.

Figure 3: TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle as displayed on the Mission’s Platform

3.1.4 Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM)

The [SJCM](#) conceptualises spatial justice by defining its three main dimensions (recognition, procedural, and distributive justice) and identifies the key components that underpin each dimension. By translating the abstract notion of justice into an operational analytical framework, the SJCM allows planners, policymakers, and researchers to systematically assess how fairness and inclusion are embedded within urban development processes.

This model complements the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJB; see section 3.1.5) by providing its theoretical foundation. This integration ensures that the conceptual model not only provides academic and theoretical insights but also supports the practical assessment and improvement of spatial justice outcomes.

Figure 4: Spatial Justice Conceptual Model as displayed on the Mission’s Platform

3.1.5 Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT)

The [SJBT](#) is a qualitative evaluation framework developed to support cities in assessing how justice considerations are integrated into urban planning, governance, and policymaking. It provides a practical means to reflect on the extent to which planning processes and outcomes account for fairness, inclusion, and equal access to urban opportunities.

The tool is based on the application of a structured assessment scale that measures different levels of justice across a series of defined criteria. These criteria enable users to examine where their city or project stands in terms of recognising and addressing spatial inequalities.

By guiding users through a reflective evaluation process, the SJBT helps cities identify areas for improvement and supports informed discussions about how to advance justice-oriented urban transformation. The tool has been designed for flexible use: it can be applied internally by city administrations or collaboratively during workshops with stakeholders.

Ultimately, the SJBT aims to raise awareness of how justice dimensions manifest in everyday planning decisions and to help cities develop more inclusive and responsive urban policies.

Figure 5: Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool as displayed on the Mission's Platform

3.1.6 Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board

The [Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board](#) is a participatory assessment instrument developed as part of the Spatial Justice Package within UP2030. It complements the SJBT by presenting its analytical framework in an interactive format for group-based evaluation and discussion.

Grounded in the three dimensions of spatial justice (recognition, procedural, and distributive), the tool provides a structured approach for examining how these principles are reflected in urban governance, planning, and design. It is intended for use in workshops or co-creation settings, where participants collectively review and discuss justice-related components of local policies or projects.

The Evaluation Board offers a practical means for cities and stakeholders to reflect on existing practices and identify ways to integrate justice considerations more consistently into urban planning and decision-making.

Figure 6: Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board as displayed on the Mission’s Platform

3.1.7 Presentation: How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?

The [Presentation “How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?”](#) provides an overview of how the concept of spatial justice can be applied to evaluate urban sustainability transition plans. It introduces spatial justice as a framework for understanding how social, environmental, and spatial factors interact in urban planning and highlights its importance in promoting equitable and inclusive urban transitions.

Developed as part of UP2030’s Spatial Justice package, the presentation summarises a comparative analysis of city plans using the SJCM and the SJBT. It illustrates how these tools can help identify gaps in recognising, addressing, and integrating justice considerations into strategic planning processes.

Figure 7: Presentation “How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?” as displayed on the Mission’s Platform

Additional resources under preparation

In addition to the seven resources already published on the Mission Platform, two further outputs were in the process of being finalised for upload. These resources have been completed at project level but were not yet ready for publication on the Platform at the time of submission of this deliverable. They are expected to be shared once the remaining technical requirements are completed. The following paragraphs provide an overview of these additional resources.

3.1.8 [Massive Open Online Course \(MOOC\)](#)

The MOOC is an online training programme designed to support urban practitioners and consultants in integrating climate neutrality, urban resilience, and spatial justice into planning and governance processes. The course provides a structured introduction to key concepts, tools, and methods developed within UP2030.

Delivered as a MOOC, the programme includes a series of video-based modules combining theoretical foundations, methodological guidance, practical tutorials, and examples from UP2030's city partners. The MOOC offers flexible learning and can be followed either as a full programme or as stand-alone video capsules, depending on learners' needs.

The curriculum is organised into five modules that have been formulated around the 5UP approach (Updating, Upskilling, Upgrading, Upscaling, and Uptaking) to resonate with the project's identity and narrative, and to capitalise on the diverse outcomes of the UP2030 project. They collectively:

- Provide an introduction to climate-neutral, resilient, and just urban transitions;
- Build capacities for co-designing visions, pathways, and prototypes;
- Support implementation and adaptation of planning practices;
- Offer guidance for scaling solutions, aligning governance structures, and mobilising financial resources;
- Encourage knowledge uptake and participation in wider communities of practice.

The MOOC aims to equip participants with practical skills, accessible tools, and inspiration for applying integrated urban transformation approaches in their professional contexts.

3.1.9 [UP2030 Service Platform](#)

The UP2030 Service Platform is a knowledge hub designed to support cities and urban districts in advancing climate neutrality, resilience, and spatial justice. It provides access to curated solutions, practical guidance, and strategic tools that help local authorities design, implement, and upscale sustainable urban planning approaches.

Developed under the project's upscaling principle, the platform enables cities to explore science-based tools and methodologies created within UP2030, including Urban Typologies and the Upscaling Toolbox. These resources offer insights on governance, finance, and policy design, and support the replication or adaptation of successful interventions across different urban contexts.

By offering structured guidance, policy recommendations, and examples of good practice, the UP2030 Service Platform helps cities strengthen their planning processes and address challenges related to climate action, resilience building, and inclusive urban development.

4 Dissemination and sharing activities

The dissemination and sharing activities described in this deliverable focused on ensuring the visibility, accessibility, and usability of UP2030 outputs within the framework of the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. These activities centred on the operational upload and communication of selected resources to the Mission's Platform and on maintaining alignment with related Mission initiatives to maximise relevance and coherence.

4.1 Upload of resources to the Mission's Platform

A liaison was created with the NZC Mission's Platform team to identify and prepare a selected list of UP2030 resources suitable for publication. Each resource underwent an internal review process to ensure completeness, consistency, and compliance with the Platform's requirements.

As demonstrated previously, the following resources were uploaded and made publicly accessible:

- Citizen Mapping Tool
- Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality
- TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle
- Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM)
- Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT)
- Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool: Evaluation Board
- Presentation: How Just Are Urban Sustainability Transition Plans?

And two additional resources were in the process of being uploaded:

- Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)
- UP2030 Service Platform

The upload process included the provision of descriptions, relevant links, and associated visuals to facilitate discoverability and usability for Mission Cities and other users. Confirmation of publication was received through direct communication with NZC representatives.

4.2 Collaboration and liaison with the Mission's Platform

Collaboration with NZC was an essential part of the process to ensure that all materials uploaded from UP2030 were consistent with the Mission's broader framework. This coordination helped align UP2030's outputs with the technical standards applied across the Platform, thereby facilitating their integration within the shared repository of Mission resources.

Exchanges between ICLEI Europe, Fraunhofer, and NZC took place during the preparation phase to clarify the upload procedures, timelines, and requirements.

As project coordinator, Fraunhofer oversaw the overall process, verifying that each resource selected for upload was complete, accurate, and aligned with the objectives of the project. This included checking that all materials were final and publicly available. NZC provided quality assurance by reviewing the final versions of the resources and confirming their compliance with the Platform's requirements before submission.

The exchanges with NZC supported the visibility of UP2030's results within the Mission ecosystem. This collaborative approach contributed to the effective publication of the project's tools and frameworks

on the Mission's Platform, ensuring consistency and reliability of the information made available to Mission Cities and stakeholders.

4.3 Visibility and promotion

To ensure visibility and accessibility beyond the Mission's Platform, the uploaded materials have been actively promoted through UP2030's communication channels. Announcements about the publication of the resources were shared internally with project partners and disseminated externally through existing communication channels, such as social media and the project newsletter, providing short descriptions and direct links to the Mission's Platform to facilitate access for Mission Cities and other interested stakeholders.

The shared tools and resources have also been communicated within the Urban Planning and Design Cluster, allowing sister projects and their pilot cities to access the UP2030 materials and explore potential synergies or applications within their own contexts. This exchange supported cross-project learning and helped ensure that the outputs could benefit a wider community of Mission-related cities.

These actions ensured the visibility of the resources among Mission Cities and stakeholders, strengthened awareness of UP2030's contributions to the Mission's knowledge base, and may support the continued use and adaptation of its tools by cities.

4.4 Outcomes

Through these dissemination activities, UP2030 ensured that its most transferable tools and policy outputs are now accessible to Mission Cities and stakeholders across Europe. The integration of these materials into the Mission's Platform contributes to the collective knowledge base supporting climate-neutral urban transitions.

The integration of UP2030's resources within the Mission's Platform expands their reach, making them available to a wide range of actors involved in other Mission and Horizon Europe projects. These resources now provide accessible references that can support participatory planning, inclusive governance and justice-oriented evaluation in cities and may be used by stakeholders seeking practical examples or methods to inform their work.

The sharing process also contributed to continued cooperation with the sister projects, facilitating the exchange of information and experiences related to the use of project tools and approaches. Aligning these outputs increases the potential for their use and adaptation in future European initiatives.

Overall, these dissemination activities improve the long-term visibility and accessibility of UP2030 results. They reflect the project's contribution to the Mission's objectives of supporting replication, capacity-building, and knowledge exchange among cities, helping ensure that the resources developed through UP2030 remain available for use.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the process and outcomes of sharing UP2030's key outputs with the Mission's Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Platform. The work aimed to ensure that the project's most transferable and practical results are available to Mission Cities and other stakeholders engaged in advancing urban climate-neutrality.

The preparation and upload of materials were carried out collaboratively by Fraunhofer and ICLEI Europe, in close coordination with NZC. This process included the selection and review of resources, followed by their publication on the Platform.

The shared materials provide Mission Cities and related initiatives with practical tools and references for participatory planning, inclusive governance, stakeholder engagement, and justice-oriented urban evaluation. They represent UP2030's contribution to the broader knowledge base supporting the Mission and can inform ongoing and future work on climate-neutral urban transitions across Europe.

By making these resources publicly accessible, UP2030 supports the continued use, adaptation, and replication of its methodologies beyond the project's duration. This dissemination effort reinforces the project's commitment to transparency, collaboration, and knowledge sharing within the Mission ecosystem, ensuring that the lessons and outputs developed under UP2030 remain available to support cities in their transition towards a more sustainable, climate-neutral future